

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACCOUNTING INFORMATION AND THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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D.O.I.: 10.5281/zenodo.19698741

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Received: 26th January, 2026
Accepted: 25th February, 2026
Published: 27th March, 2026

KEYWORDS: Accounting Information Systems, Financial Performance, Private Schools, Akwa Ibom State

Journal url:
<https://ijois.com/index.php/jobpef>

Editor-in-chief: Assist. Prof. Dr (C) Ari Riswanto

PUBLISHER: Empirical Studies and Communication – (A Research Center) Website:
www.cescd.com.ng

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between accounting information systems (AIS) and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. Employing a survey design, primary data were collected via a structured questionnaire administered to staff in accounting and related departments of private schools across the three senatorial districts (Uyo, Eket, Ikot Ekpene). The sampling approach combined purposive (judgmental) selection with multi-stage techniques: stratification to identify metropolitan private schools within local government areas, followed by targeted distribution of 300 questionnaires; 250 were returned; after screening for completeness, 190 valid responses were analyzed. The instrument comprised sections on demographics, AIS hardware, software, database, network communication technology, system maintenance and users' competence, and financial performance. Responses were measured on a five-point Likert scale (SA = 5 to SD = 1). Instrument reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha (overall $\alpha = 0.826$), indicating acceptable internal consistency, while face validity was established through expert review. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics and simple linear regression to test hypotheses relating AIS components (hardware and software) to financial performance. Results show statistically significant positive relationships for both hardware ($R = 0.842, p < 0.05$) and software ($R = 0.816, p < 0.05$), with software identified as having a particularly positive influence on performance. The study concludes that AIS notably software, database management, and network communication technologies relate positively to private schools' financial outcomes, and recommends complementary investments in software and network solutions alongside hardware procurement to realize financial benefits.

INTRODUCTION

Accounting Information systems have become a necessity in the 21st century as the world records unprecedented growth in information technology. This is due to the pervasive nature of innovative technologies that have provided solutions to a wide range of problems across every sphere of human endeavour. This has led to a wide spread application of

accounting information systems in the business world which have provide solutions to financial performance challenges and ensure improved competitive advantages.

Accounting Information System (AIS) as a veritable tool in the hands of accountants has helped accounting practices in several ways. Accounting Information System (AIS), a component of business information systems (IS), is considered to assist in decision-making in organizations and should be customized in the environment, tasks requirements and organisational structure of the organisation. Specifically, properly qualified accountants collaborate with AIS to guarantee the highest level of accuracy in a private school's financial operations and record-keeping as well as make financial data easily accessible to those who need them while maintaining data integrity and security (Al-Okaily *et al.*, 2020).

A company's financial transactions and record-keeping are guaranteed to be as accurate as possible when AIS is used. This also enhances financial data convenient accessibility to those who genuinely need it while preserving data, integrity and security. Any Private School that benefits from AIS ensures that safeguards are put in place to record and process data properly. This may help put an end to mismanagement of fund cases. It also enhances workers' morale through an efficient payroll system (Setyaningsih *et al.*, 2021). Most Private Schools have invested in accounting information system in order to track transactions and improve their financial performance. These systems cost the Private Schools a lot of money to acquire, install and maintain (Rainer *et al.* 2022).

According to Enyi *et al.* (2019), information communication technology resources consist of hardware and software, database, network communication and human components of skills, expertise, competencies, commitment, values, norms and knowledge that combine to create information technology services that are typically unique to an Organization The ICT infrastructure uses the electronic to carry out activities and basic needs at all levels in addition, ICT infrastructures means automating new processes, activities, operations, information and telecommunication using the electronic technology. The electronic technology includes: Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), internet Banking (IBN), Mobile Banking (MOB) and Point of Sales (POS). It also includes: E-mail and mobile phones.

Aws *et al.* (2020) asserted that Accounting Information System (AIS) 'involves the collection, storage and processing of financial and accounting data used by internal users to report information to investors, creditors and tax authorities. Akpanobong *et al.* (2023) studied on Financial Information System and School Budget preparation for smooth running of tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom state.

The use of accounting information systems (AIS) can improve the efficiency of the organization's accounting units. This may facilitates information processing more quickly, accurately and allows businesses to manage costs better and improve internal and external financial reporting. Accounting systems are important in the private schools because they facilitate the flow of precise financial data and improve the efficiency of the entire accounting process, enabling decision-makers to make judgments in crucial areas such as expenditure, inflow and pricing (Ali *et al.* 2021). Therefore, it is necessary to assess how accounting information system affects the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The use of accounting information system has become a critical factor in changing competitive environment of the business. For private schools to effectively and efficiently achieve positive outcome in their financial performance, a sound knowledge of the accounting

information system that regulates the operational activities of the private school needs to be understood by the users of accounting information system of such private schools. The users' understanding of the accounting information system would assist in proper decisions about the financial performance of the school. The major problems include; loose accounting records, documents, files and books not adequately kept.

The fees are collected by hand without receipts as evidence of payment with no proper documentation. Moreso, cash is the most liquid asset which might be easily tampered with and mismanaged. In addition, other problems confronting the private schools are the high cost of acquiring components for accounting information system such as hardware, software, database management, network communication technology. In the same vein, engagement of a competent accountant with requisite skill in system maintenance is required, Leonard (2018) investigated a set of IT skills that were most relevant to accountants. The Information Technology (IT) skills include the use of spread sheet and processing of application software, generic PC use (windows), utilization of e-mail for communication and the www. This reveals the need for fundamental accounting information system to be implemented by the private schools which might affect the organizations' performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between accounting information and the financial performance of Private Schools in Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- (i) examine the relationship between accounting information system hardware and financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State;
- (ii) investigate the relationship between accounting information systems software and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State;

Research Questions

Based on the specified objectives of the study, the following research questions are raised:

- (i) What is the relationship between accounting information system hardware and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State?
- (ii) What is the relationship between accounting information system software and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses will guide the conduct of this study:

- Ho₁: Accounting Information System hardware has no significant relationship with the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State.
- Ho₂: Accounting Information System software does not significantly relate positively with the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Accounting Information Systems

Accounting Information System (AIS) is a computer-based electronic system used for collecting, storing, processing and communicating financial and accounting data through financial statements to support and guide the Organizational decision-making process. (Manchilot, 2019). According to Kayed (2021) Accounting Information System is a system including a combination of accounting techniques, methodologies, controls and Information Communication Technology (ICT) and are used for tracking transactions, external reporting of data, reporting of internal data, trend analysis and financial statements reporting. Accounting information serves to improve the level of reliability of information provided by a system that is run manually without using information system technology. According to Krisnawati and Suartana (2018), information system plays a role in the field of accounting because they make it simple for users to generate accounting information that is complete, timely and easily comprehended.

The information technology infrastructure relates to the hardware that is helpful for the operation of accounting information system. The devices include: computers, servers, printers and routers among others. The hardware is usually used together with the software, therefore, there is need to ensure that both are compatible. Private schools need to consider issues such as; efficiency, speed, upgrade options and cost before acquiring any hardware. Private schools should ensure that outdated hardware is upgraded or disposed of because of continuous advancement in technology (Ganyam *et al.*, 2019). To ensure optimum working conditions, the hardware should be serviced regularly. The purpose of servicing regularly is to ensure that it is not affected by bugs.

According to Okeke (2024) fundings for ICT Hardware have a negative and insignificant effect on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study suggested that Stakeholders, especially managers in the consumer goods should always review all opinions carefully before going into procurement of additional computer hardware. Computer hardware is the physical component that a computer system needs to function. It includes all parts with a circuit board that operates within a computer (PC or Laptop, including the mother board, graphics card, Central Processing Unit, ventilation fans, webcam, power supply among others). Computers cannot function without both hardware and software working together. However, it is the hardware that determines the speed of the system. Computer software is for a collection of instructions that enables the user to interact with a computer, its hardware or perform a task.

According to Sultana (2018), software refers to the computer-based programs that are used in the gathering, processing, analyzing and storage of information. Some common accounting information systems software include: QuickBooks, Sage Accounting and Dynamic GP among others. The use of accounting software has rapidly and drastically changed in today's business environment. Globally, corporate entities are progressively implementing advanced accounting software systems to optimize their financial processes, augment the precision of the reports, as well as their overall effectiveness. The technology shift is significant for financial reporting because it could have a significant impact, dependability and timeliness for financial data obtained from private schools. There is a revolutionary role of technology in the ever-changing world of corporate finance and accounting.

Accounting software has become a vital tool for corporate companies all over the world because it helps to manage their financial data and expedite reporting procedures. In the field of financial reporting, the rapid growth of accounting software systems is a critical movement since it can greatly affect the efficiency, accuracy and quality of financial data that private schools provide. The use of accounting software by corporate bodies has grown to be a crucial aspect of financial management tactics. These programs have many functions, ranging from

automating repetitive data entry work to giving private schools real-time financial insights, enabling them to make logical decisions. However, the effects of incorporating accounting software into financial reporting procedures are extensive and require careful consideration. The financial reporting environment may be affected in a variety of ways by the integration of accounting software systems, which marks a substantial shift from traditional manual accounting techniques. This study aims to examine the relationship between the accounting information system and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Accounting Software is an application designed to meet the needs of management and other users by streamlining accounting operations and increasing speed (Thottoli, 2020). According to Owolabi and Ogunode (2020), management demands in this area include effectively carrying out their stewardship obligations. By making urgent response to embrace information technology (IT), businesses can quickly acquire and utilize accounting software to do daily accounting tasks. This is because the majority of accounting software is user-friendly, resulting in accurate and timely accounting operations (Xu, 2020). In addition, the necessity for an integrated accounting information system in the form of accounting software has become increasingly apparent due to the quick rise of new markets, globalization and related economic activities (Draijer, 2020).

Database Management and Accounting Information Systems

An accounting information system is the collection, storage and processing of financial and accounting data by an organization for various stakeholders, both internal users and external users. The external users such as investors, creditors, tax authority, among others (Alicia, 2020). An Accounting Information System is generally a computer-based method that is used for tracking accounting activities in conjunction with Information Technology resources. A well-designed accounting information system helps businesses to run smoothly, enhances different departments within the company to work together and protect sensitive data of the company.

According to Craig (2024), a database is an organized collection of structured information or data, specifically used to store information on people, places, among others in a computer system. It is not only for collection of files but also for their organization within the context of some applications which require persistent storage and online access. For example, if a student's information is created, there would be need to have the name, address, date of birth, health status, fees paid, debt profile, name of parents/guardians' contact, phone numbers, among others. The database is helpful to search and sort the required information. Data stored in databases is usually used to make informed business decisions. Databases require some operating and maintaining challenges, such as data security, data integrity, database performance and data integration. An Accounting Information System must have a database structure to store information. An example is Structured Query Language (SQL). Structured Query Language is a commonly used computer language in database systems. SQL enhances the manipulation and retrieval of the data stored within the Accounting Information System. The data normally used within an Accounting Information Systems is every financial information that is relevant to the private schools' business practices. This means that the data that impact the finances of the private school should be included and stored inside the database of the Accounting Information System. The stored data could be used to create accounting statements and financial reports. Keeping all the data in a particular place which relates to Accounting Information System helps the private school to be more efficient in record keeping,

reporting, analysis, auditing and decision-making. The data stored within an Accounting Information System might be Purchase requisitions, Inventory data, Payroll information, Tax information, among others.

According to Alexander *et al.* (2024) a Database stores essential data, which is valuable information for a private school and helps in the decision-making process. Databases help accounting information systems manipulate and analyze large amounts of historical data, which helps businesses uncover valuable insights within their financials, identify and process improvements that can increase efficiency and better risk management. Databases can hold a million historical records of students, which is important for private schools. The structure is typically programmed with query language, which allows users to manipulate table and data. Furthermore, the accounting information that is stored in databases is often highly secured platforms with preventive measures against viruses, hackers and other external sources. This is why data security is important, as more and more private schools store their data electronically.

Financial Performance

Borhan and Badar (2018) opine that Accounting Information System is made up of a group of harmonized businesses, components and resources that process, manage, control the data for producing and convey relevant information for decision makers in the Organization. Considered differently, Kashif (2018), notes that, Accounting Information System relates to people, equipment, policies and procedures in functioning effectively to collect, process and transfer data into useful information. The objectives of Accounting Information System include: collecting and storing of data, processing data into information useable for decision making, performing effective control over a company asset and the systematic presentation of financial data in an accurate manner. Associating Accounting Information System with financial performance, Letizia *et al.* (2022), disagree that, it affects employee performance at Banco Nasional de Comercio de Timor-hesta (BNCTL). In their opinion, these authors concerted that, this happens since a good accounting Information System will provide access to the customer services completely, safely, quickly, easily and will give accurate, effective and efficient financial reporting and recording.

According to Borhan and Nafees (2018), financial performance states the status of an organization's financial health, its capability to meet its long-term financial obligations and its commitment to provide services in the future at a particular period. Financial performance refers to requirements of performing financial activity. In a broader sense, financial performance refers to the extent of which financial objectives have been accomplished. It is the process of measuring the outcome of firms' policies and operations in monetary terms. Financial performance is generally viewed as the ability of the firm to meet its financial objectives. There are two major indicators of financial performance being: investors' return and accounting returns. The investors' return is measured from the perspective of stakeholders whereas accounting returns focus on how the earning respond to different managerial policies (Ganyam, 2019).

Measuring the financial performance of the private schools is done using different measures (Kashif, 2018). According to Akanbi and Adewoye (2018). It usually employs the financial ratio method because it provides a simple description about the firm's financial performance in comparison with previous periods and assists to improve the performance of management. The financial performance might be measured using return on total assets (ROTA), net operating profit (NOP), gross profit margin (GPM), returns on capital employed (ROCE), liquidity ratio (LR) and current ratio (CR) among others. Accounting Information Systems (AIS), which are a component of business information systems (IS), are meant to aid

in decision-making of the firms. The accounting information system is customized to the environment, task requirements and organizational structure of the organization. Specifically, in clear terms, qualified accountants make use of Accounting Information System to guarantee the highest level of accuracy in a company's financial operations and record-keeping to make financial data easily accessible to those who need it while maintaining data integrity and security (Al-Okaily *et al.*, 2020).

A company's financial transaction and record-keeping are guaranteed to be as accurate as possible due to Accounting Information System, which also makes financial data conveniently accessible to those who genuinely need it while preserving data integrity and security. Any private school could benefit from AIS since it ensures that safeguards are put in place to properly record and process data. This would help to put an end to cases of mismanagement of funds. It also enhances workers' morale through an efficient payroll system (Setijani-ngsih *et-al.*, 2021). Most private schools have invested in accounting information systems in order to track transactions and improve their performance. These systems cost the firms large sums of money to acquire, install and maintain them in good condition (Rainer and Prince, 2022).

The use of accounting information systems (AIS) can improve the efficiency of various sections of the accounting department. This facilitates information processing more quickly, accurately and allow companies to manage costs better and improve internal and external financial reporting. Accounting systems are necessary in the private school because they facilitate the flow of precise financial data and improve the efficiency of the entire accounting process, enabling decision makers to make judgments in crucial areas such as expenditure, inflow and budgeting (Ali and Oudat, 2021).

According to Kayed (2021), AIS is a system encompassing a combination of accounting techniques, methodologies, controls and Information Communication Technology (ICT) used for tracking transactions, external reporting of data, reporting of internal data and trend analysis as well as financial statements reporting. In a slightly different explanation to the research findings of Kayed (2021), Manchilot (2019) opined that AIS is a computer-based electronic system used for collecting, storing, processing and communicating financial and accounting data through financial statements to support and guide the organizational decision-making process. In the empirical assertion of Muhammadi and Seif (2019), firms that adopt accounting information systems are more likely to achieve higher financial performance. Thus, financial performance refers to the ability of the firm to achieve its goals and objectives, which could be financial or non-financial. In this study, it is important that AIS will further enhance the financial performance of private schools.

Theoretical Review

Technology Acceptance Model

This theory was propounded by Davis (1989). The theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) was modified by Davis (1989) into the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM), which is designed primarily for simulating used adoption of information technology. The objective of TAM is to offer an explanation for the factors that determine whether or not people accept computers in general and are able to rationally and sparingly explain user behavior across a wide range of end-user computing technologies and user groups. In a perfect world, a model would be useful for both explanation and prediction, allowing academics and practitioners to determine why a given system might be problematic and take the necessary collective action (Marangunic and Granic, 2015). To trace the impact of external factors on internal beliefs, attitudes and intentions are some of the main goals of TAM (Chen *et al.*, 2017). In an effort to

accomplish these goals, TAM was established by selecting a small number of fundamental variables that had been suggested by earlier research on the cognitive and framework for modelling the theoretical relationships between these variables (Marangunic and Granic, 2015). The TAM highlights broad aspects of prospective technology acceptance solutions and obstacles, it has been demonstrated to be of help as a theoretical model for elucidating and comprehending user behavior in the adoption of accounting information systems.

Empirical Review

Hassan *et al.* (2023) examined effect of accounting information system on the quality of financial reporting of listed Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The focus was on the process by which the financial reports are produced. Primary data was used on the administration of questionnaire to 276 respondents selected for the study. The variables used included system quality, user competence, faithful representation relevance, timeliness and understandability. The Structural Equation Modelling was used to analyze the data collected. The findings of the study revealed that system quality ($B=0.342$) $p=0.000<0.001$, $t=3.107>1.96$, have significant and positive effect on the quality of financial reporting. Hardware alone showed negative effect on the financial performance. The study recommended that firms should always maintain a high quality of their AIS through constant update of the AIS hardware and software to meet up with the demands for quality financial reporting. In addition, firms should employ people who are sound and competent in using the AIS and knowledgeable in financial reporting standards to prepare the financial reports.

Okeke (2024) examined the effect of information and communication technology (ICT) on firm performance and showed how it has become the subject of much research in the past forty years. The focus of this study was to review the effect of ICT on the financial performance of firms in the consumer goods sector as measured by their Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) with the size of the firm added as a control variable from 2013 to 2022. The study used 13 listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. An *ex-post facto* research approach was used and secondary data were obtained from the companies' annual reports for the period under review. E-views version 12 was used to do a correlation and regression analysis. The findings show that funding for ICT hardware and funding for ICT software (FICTS) have a negative and insignificant effect on the financial performance of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study should that stakeholders, especially managers in the consumer goods sector should always review all options carefully before considering any procurement of additional computer hardware or software bearing in mind the negative impact of their ROCE.

Jeff (2024) examined the mobile accounting software and financial performance of small-scale hotels in Mombasa, Kenya. The utilization of accounting software, which includes various modules like trial balance, payroll accounts receivable and accounts payable, improved efficiency through task automation and error reduction. Mobile applications, accessible through platforms such as Google Play Store and Apple Store, further enhance financial processes for SME proprietors providing instant access to financial data and invoice tracking and their combined impact on financial performance. Empirical data from different nations, such as Indonesia and Germany, highlight the advantages of these apps in enhancing financial literacy and management capabilities among SME owners. Specifically, in areas like Tudor ward, Mombasa, Kenya, the awareness and utilization of mobile accounting software is crucial for attaining heightened efficiency, transparency and financial advancement for SMEs. As technology progresses, its role in bolstering the financial well-being and endurance of small enterprises will grow increasingly important. The accounting software has a significant and positive effect on the financial performance of small-scale hotels in Mombasa, Kenya.

Richard *et al.* (2022) examined the linking of computerised accounting information system adoption to financial performance in the Public Sector the influence of internal control systems in the linkage between the drivers of s (CAIS) adoption and financial performance of the Public Sector. Data was collected from the operators and controllers of CAIS of 227 local governments across the sixteen regions of Ghana using the questionnaire as the main instrument. The structural equation modelling was employed to analyze the hypothesized relationships between the drivers of CAIS adoption and financial performance and the mediating role of internal control. The findings showed that there are link between interventions by government to improve technology adoption among local governments such ICT education, training, emphasis on strengthening internal controls and awareness creation programmes among key controllers of the local government. In addition, local government should consider adopting CAIS technology on the basis of software-as-a service also known as cloud account in an attempt to deal with the cost of managing accounting information system. The accounting information system software has a positive and significant impact on the financial performance on public sector in Ghana.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study used the survey design approach. This approach provided the researcher the requisite tools for obtaining information from the sampled population. The choice of this design became necessary because anonymity allow respondents to answer with no bias and provide valid responses to the research enquiry.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised private schools duly registered in Akwa Ibom State. The information which generated the data used for this study was obtained from the Ministry of Education, State Headquarters Secretariat, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State in September, 2024. The available information showed a total of 1639 private schools made up of 17 Tertiary Institutions, 499 Secondary schools and 1123 Primary/Nursery/Crèche Schools. The respondent's population was the members of staff of Accounting Department and other Departments which are related to Accounts Departments of Private Schools that are computer-based using accounting information system.

Sample/Sampling Techniques

In this study the Purposive (Judgmental) sampling technique was used for the determination of sampling size. Multi-stage sampling techniques comprising of three stages was used to determine the sample size. The first stage was the use of the stratified sampling method. The use of the stratified sampling method was to identify the private schools which are located in the metropolitan cities of respective Local Government Areas in the three Senatorial Districts. The three senatorial district are: Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene. Out of the 300 copies of questionnaire distributed, the researcher was able to collect 250 copies from the respondents. From the 250 copies, some respondents made mistakes and did not fill correctly and properly. The questionnaire with mistakes, not properly filled were rejected and not used for this study. From the 250 copies, the number of questionnaire properly and correctly filed was 190 copies, used for this study.

Source of Data

The main data used for the study were from primary source which were questionnaire administered to private schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used for this study was the questionnaire. The questionnaire was constructed by the researcher under the guidance of the supervisor and administered to the owners/management, members of staff of accounting departments of the schools studied and other departments that are related to accounting departments of the private schools. The instrument contained questions on accounting information systems and financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. Section A consisted of four questions requiring demographic information on the respondents. Section B assessed accounting hardware, Section C focused on accounting software, Section D assessed database. Section E focused on network communication technology, Section F assessed system maintenance and user's (operator's) competence as it relates to accounting information system and Section G assessed the financial performance.

The five point Likert scale was used to measure the questionnaire statements as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) – 5 points, Agree (A) 4 points Neutral (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1 point. This was used to indicate the degree of agreement or disagreement with each of the questionnaire statements which measured the independent variable, accounting information system and the dependent variable, financial performance of private schools.

Reliability Test of Research Instrument

In terms of instrument reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was used in testing the study's reliability. The overall result of the test analysis was 0.826. This showed the instrument was reliable as the Cronbach reliability values were above the acceptable benchmark of 0.70 and shown to be good enough for use in research. the Cronbach Alpha results from the studied variables shows overall Cronbach alpha results of 82.56%. This signifies reliability as postulated by Griethuijzen *et al.* (2014).

Validity Test of Instrument

To ensure that the instrument was valid for use in the study, the research instrument was presented to the Supervisor and other Senior Lecturers in the Department of Accounting. The Supervisor and other Senior Lecturers made useful inputs that led to the modification of the questionnaire. Therefore, the instrument had face validity which is important in research.

Model Specification and Description of Variables

In order to investigate the relationship between independent variable, accounting information systems and dependent variable, Private School's financial performance, the following model was developed.

$$y = f(x)$$

Where y = Dependent Variable

x = Independent Variable

$$y = a + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e$$

Equation 3.1

Where,

y = Dependent Variable (Private Schools Financial Performance)

x = Accounting Information System

Where,

X₁ = Hardware

X₂ = Software

X₃ = Database

X₄ = Network Communication Technology

X₅ = System Maintenance and User's Competence

a = y intercept

$\beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \beta_4 + \beta_5$ = the regression coefficients of the four independent variables

e = Error

Data Presentation, Analysis and Findings

Research Question One

What is the relationship between accounting information system hardware and financial performance of the private schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4.1: Frequency and percentages showing relationship between accounting information's system hardware and financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. (n=190).

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	High cost of computer hardware (Desktop) has prevented your school from the benefits of the computerized Accounting Information System (AIS)	95 (50%)	57 (30%)	0 (0%)	24 12.6%	14 7.4%
2.	Cost of Hardware Components such as keyboards, mouse, display terminals, printers, epod, has hindered deployment of accounting hardware for usage by your school.	84 44.2(%)	69 36.3(%)	3 1.6(%)	13 6.8(%)	21 11.1(%)
3.	Special input devices tailored to meet the needs of private school such as optical character Reader (OCR), magnetic ink character readers (MICRs), and others has prevented your school from using computer based system to process accounting information.	74 38.9(%)	61 38.9(%)	3 1.6(%)	17 8.9(%)	35 18.4(%)
4.	Output devices tailored to meet the needs of your school such as visual display units, plotters, among has ensured the timeliness of AIS reports such as Comprehensive Income Statement, among others.	91 47.9(%)	83 43.7(%)	NIL NIL	3 2.7(%)	13 6.8(%)
5.	Communication support system like MODEM, and other hardware support systems has enhanced AIS in your school.	101 53.2(%)	81 42.7(%)	NIL NIL	3 1.6(%)	5 2.6(%)

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025).

The results in Table 1 indicate the relationship between accounting information systems hardware and financial performance in private schools in Akwa Ibom State. A significant majority respondents of 95(50% and 57 (30%) agreed that the high cost of computer hardware is a significant barrier preventing private schools from benefiting from computerized accounting information systems. while a minority 24(12.6%) and 14(7.4%) disagreed. Most respondents 84(44.2%) and 69(36.3%) agreed that cost of hardware components such as keyboards, mouse, display terminals, printers, epod, has hindered the deployment of accounting hardware for use by private schools. Three respondents, representing were 3(1.6%) neutral, 13(6.8%) and 21 11.1%) disagreed:

Most respondents 74 (38.9% and 61(32.1%) agreed that special input devices tailored to meet the needs of private school such as the optical character Reader (OCR), magnetic ink character readers (MICRs), and others have prevented private schools from using computer-based system to process accounting information. A smaller portion of respondents 3 (1.6%)

neutral, 17 (8.9% and 35(18.4%) disagreed respondents 91(47.9%) and 83 (43.7%) agreed in their opinion that output devices tailored to meet the needs of schools such as visual display units, plotters, among other devices have ensured the timely preparation of AIS reports such as Comprehensive Income Statement and financial position, among others. A smaller respondent 5(2.7%) and 36.8(%) disagreed. A large segment of respondents 101(53.2%) and 81(42.7%) agreed that communication support system like MODEM, and other hardware support systems has enhanced AIS in private school. The minority 3(1.6%) and 5(2.6%) disagreed.

In support of the opinion of this result, it is good to note that a significant majority of the respondents 95(50% and 57 (30%) agreed that the high cost of computer hardware is a significant inhibitor preventing private schools from benefiting from computerized accounting information systems. while a minority 24(12.6% and 14(7.4%) disagreed. According to records and researcher's firsthand experience with respondents, the high cost of computer hardware is indeed a significant barrier preventing private schools, especially those with limited financial resources, from adopting computerized accounting systems. This challenge is not unique to private schools but is prevalent across various educational institutions in Nigeria. Private schools, especially those with limited financial resources, may struggle to afford the cost of purchasing computers, servers, and networking equipment required for computerized accounting.

Research question Two:

What is the relationship between accounting information software and financial performance in private schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4.2: Frequency and percentages (%) showing relationship between accounting information software and financial performance in private schools (n=190).

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Relevant accounting software costs has prevented your school from deploying them in enhancing AIS	81 42.6(%)	77 40.5(%)	NIL NIL	14 7.4(%)	18 9.5(%)
2.	Accounting software such as Budget Master, SAGE, Quickbooks have ensured AIS effectiveness in your school.	94 49.5(%)	68 35.8(%)	NIL NIL	11 5.8%	17 8.0(%)
3.	Software facilities/utility programs have enhanced report generation and clarity in your school.	88 46.5(%)	71 37.4(%)	NIL NIL	8 4.2(%)	23 12.7(%)
4.	Computer accounting softwares prompt ease of data analysis and usage in your school	102 53.7(%)	61 32.1(%)	NIL NIL	6 3.2(%)	21 11.1(%)
5.	Accounting software enhances system and data security as well as keeping log in your school	103 54.2(%)	59 31.1(%)	NIL NIL	9 4.7(%)	19 10(%)

Table 2 illustrates the relationship between the use of information software and the financial performance of the private schools studied. Out of the 190 respondents surveyed, larger proportion of 81(42.6%) and 77(40.5%) respondents agreed that relevant accounting software costs has prevented private school from deploying them in enhancing AIS. In contrast, a smaller proportion of 14(7.4%) and 18(9.5%) disagreed. A significant majority of 94(49.5%)

and 68 (35.8%) agreed in their opinion that accounting software such as Budget Master, SAGE, Quickbooks has ensured AIS effectiveness in private school. The minorities of 11(5.8%) and 17 (8.9%) disagreed. A significant majority of 88(43.3%) and 71(37.4%) agreed that Software facilities/utility programs enhance report generation and clarity in private school. The larger segment of 102(53.7%) and 61(32.1%) respondents agreed that computer accounting softwares prompt ease of data analysis and usage in private school. Smaller segment of 6(3.2%) and 21 respondents (11.1%) disagreed.

The majority of 103(54.2%) and 59(31.1%) agreed that accounting software enhances system and data security as well as keeping log in private school. Minority 9(4.7)/and 19(10%) disagreed. Findings of this study indicates that a greater number of participants 102 (53.7%) and 61 (32.1%) believe software and computer systems improve the accuracy of records, facilitate the summarization of accounting records, and enable the easy maintenance of payroll systems. Therefore, accounting information system software has positive and significant relationship to the financial performance.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses One

Null Hypothesis one states that there is no significant relationship between accounting information system hardware and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. In order to answer the hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis was performed on the data (Table 3-5).

Table 4.7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change
1	0.842	0.709	0.705	4.281	0.709

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	5963.24	1	5963.24		
Residual	2437.56	188	12.96	325.48	0.000*
Total	8400.80	189			

Significant at 0.05 level; df = 2, 188; N = 190; Critical r-value = 0.138

Table 5: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-cal	Sig.
	(β)	Std. Error	(Beta)		
(Constant)	11.254	1.423		18.04	0.4.88
Hardware	0.894	0.050	0.842	7.91	0.4.88

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Accounting Information System Hardware

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

The calculated R-value (0.842) is far greater than the critical r-value (0.138) at 0.05 significance level, and the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05. This indicates a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between accounting information system hardware and the

financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that AIS hardware significantly influences financial performance.

Hypothesis Two

Null Hypothesis two states that there is no significant relationship between software of accounting information systems and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. In order to answer the hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis was performed on the data (Table 6-8).

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change
1	0.816	0.666	0.663	4.693	0.666

Table 7: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	5594.84	1	5594.84		
Residual	4155.96	188	22.11	253.29	0.000*
Total	9750.80	189			

Significant at 0.05 level; df = 2, 188; N = 190; Critical r-value = 0.138

Table 8: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-cal	Sig.
	(β)	Std. Error	(Beta)		
(Constant)	10.742	1.572		6.83	0.000
Software	0.915	0.058	0.816	15.91	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Software of Accounting Information Systems

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The calculated R-value (0.816) is substantially greater than the critical r-value (0.138) at the 0.05 level of significance. Additionally, the p-value (0.000) is below 0.05, indicating a strong, positive, and statistically significant relationship between the software of accounting information systems and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that AIS software significantly influences financial performance.

Discussion of Findings

The regression results show that hardware has a negative and insignificant effect on financial performance, with a coefficient of 0.894 and a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that, in this model, hardware alone does not contribute meaningfully to good financial performance. This finding contrasts with some studies that emphasize hardware as a foundational component of technological infrastructure necessary for business operations. For instance, Feng *et al.* (2019) argued that robust hardware investments are essential for sustaining operational efficiency. However, similar to the findings here, Manar *et al.* (2021) noted that hardware's impact on financial outcomes may be less significant when considered independently, suggesting that without complementary investments in software or network technologies,

hardware upgrades alone may not drive financial improvements. This study supports the view that the isolated impact of hardware may be minimal and that it likely serves as a foundational rather than a performance-enhancing factor.

Software has a highly significant positive effect on financial performance, with a coefficient of 0.915 (p-value = 0.000) and a Beta value of 0.816. This shows that software plays a crucial role in driving financial performance, aligning with studies by Phyu and Vongurai (2020), which found out that high-quality software applications contribute to better data processing, customer relationship management, and decision-making, which collectively enhance financial outcomes. Furthermore, Situmorang (2020) demonstrated that software investments, particularly in enterprise resource planning (ERP) and customer management systems, directly correlate with financial performance, as efficient software optimizes internal operations. The findings in this study reinforce the notion that investing in software is crucial for financial success, underscoring software's role in adding value across functional areas.

Conclusion

Based on findings in this study, there is a relationship between accounting information system and performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State. However, there is no positive and significant relationship between accounting information system hardware and financial performance of selected private schools; a positive and significant relationship between the accounting information software and the financial performance of selected private schools; the database management systems enhance data accuracy, accessibility and analytical capabilities leading to improved financial decision-making. The accounting information system network communication technology has a positive and significant effect on financial performance as well as enhances communication, collaboration and information flow within and outside an organization.

Recommendations

Based on findings from this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Since hardware alone has a negative and no significant effect on financial performance, there is need for complementary investments in software, network technologies among others.
- ii. High quality software has a significantly positive influence on financial performances; there is need for software investments particularly in enterprise resource planning (ERP) by the management.
- iii. The database management is vital for financial success, hence there is the need to optimize resource allocation and respond to market changes for achieving financial performance.

Suggestions for further studies

In this study, the impact generated by accounting information system and the financial performance of private schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria was studied. The study made use of 30 schools. Other researchers should consider expanding the number to about 45. This study used only three variables, future studies might consider other components of ICT other than the three used in the present study. In the same vein, future studies might investigate challenges facing private schools in adopting AIS and how such challenges impact their set goals.

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